

Growth and scintillation performances of SrI₂:Eu with low activator concentration

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Abstract

SrI₂:Eu crystals with the activator content of 0.1-5.5% were grown by the Bridgman-Stockbarger technique. The dependences of light yield, energy resolution, optical and luminescent properties on the Eu concentration have been studied. It has been shown that with a decrease in the amount of activator to 0.3% Eu, the energy resolution at 662 keV remains below 4%. The light yield gradually decreases with decreasing Eu concentration. This makes it possible to revise the required amount of the expensive activator for growing high performance SrI₂:Eu crystals. Scintillation parameters of crystals grown by the Czochralski and Bridgman-Stockbarger methods have been compared.

Keywords: A1 Doping, A2 Single crystal growth, A2 Bridgman technique, B1 Halides, Scintillator materials.

Declarations of interest: none.

1. Introduction

Strontium iodide activated by Europium has been known as scintillation material since 1968 [1]. However, at the time of discovery, it didn't attract much attention because of the moderate light yield and energy resolution, as well as a very high hygroscopicity. Recently, the SrI₂:Eu scintillation performance have been significantly improved by optimizing the growth process by different techniques and raw material purity [2-5]. The best published SrI₂:Eu parameters correspond to a scintillation yield of 115,000 ph/MeV and an energy resolution of 2.8% at the 662 keV energy γ -quanta excitation by a ¹³⁷Cs source [6]. These characteristics are comparable with LaBr₃:Ce, one of the most efficient inorganic scintillators [7].

Despite the excellent scintillation parameters, application of strontium iodide detectors is limited due to the high cost. The hygroscopic starting components cost is typically several k\$/kg for SrI₂ and over 10k\$/kg for EuI₂. Thus, the required amount of activator is particularly critical. The optimal amount of activator for obtaining high-quality crystal was shown to be around 5% [6, 8]. In such conditions the raw material cost for ~5% Eu-doped SrI₂ doubles with respect to the non-activated crystal. Despite the close ionic radii of Sr²⁺ and Eu²⁺, the introduction of high activator concentrations also increases the probability of ingot cracking due to not completely uniform activator distribution in the volume.

It was shown [9] that with an optimized raw material preparation procedure [2] and the activator content of around 0.5% Eu a high energy resolution of 3.5% can be achieved in SrI₂:Eu crystals grown by the Czochralski technique. As EuI₂ likely can play a role of both luminescence activator, and admixture scavenger in halide melts [10, 11], it was assumed that lower Eu content can satisfy the required properties when using raw materials of the optimized quality. To check and confirm the result obtained with Czochralski crystals [9], and to exclude the factor of crystal growth method, in this work SrI₂:Eu crystals were grown in the concentration range of 0.1-5.5% Eu using the Bridgman technique in order to demonstrate the possibility of reducing the cost of

the initial components for crystal growth. The impact of Eu concentration on optical and scintillation characteristics was studied and compared to samples fabricated from Czochralski-grown crystals.

2. Experimental

2.1. Raw materials and crystal growth

Raw materials from APL Engineered Materials with a purity of 99.99% with the pH level of 3-4 [2] were used at crystal growth. The raw materials were loaded into quartz ampoules in a dry box. The internal diameter of the ampoules was 20 mm. The growing was carried out in the two-zone Bridgman-Stockbarger furnace. The growth rate was 1 mm/hour. After completion of growth and unpacking the ampoules the samples without cracks were extracted from middle parts of the ingots, nearly at the same distance from the ampoule top and then polished with an abrasive paper in a dry atmosphere for study of their optical and scintillation parameters. The samples were 7 mm thick with the diameter of around 15 mm. The actual Eu^{2+} concentrations in crystals were determined by complexometric titration.

2.2. Optical measurements

To measure the absorption and luminescence spectra the polished samples were placed in sealed containers with quartz windows. Absorption spectra of crystals were measured with a Specord Analytik Jena 40 spectrometer. Emission spectra under VUV excitation were measured using a combined fluorescent lifetime and steady-state spectrometer FLS 920 (Edinburgh Instruments). A Xe lamp was used for steady-state measurements, and a nanosecond hydrogen-filled flashlamp was used for decay time measurements. X-ray luminescence (RL) spectra were measured using a home-made apparatus featuring a charge-coupled device (CCD) detector

(Jobin-Yvon Spectrum One 3000) coupled to a monochromator (Jobin-Yvon Triax 180). RL irradiation was performed by a Philips 2274 X-ray tube set at 35 kV.

2.3. Scintillation measurements

Measurements of light yield and energy resolution were performed in a room with a humidity below 0.1%. Light output and energy resolution under irradiation with 662 keV γ -quanta, ^{137}Cs isotope were determined from amplitude spectra of $\text{SrI}_2:\text{Eu}$ samples by the photopeak channel number and full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the peak, correspondingly. Before measuring the scintillation characteristics, the samples were additionally polished with a mixture of alcohols. Samples were coupled to a photomultiplier (PMT) photocathode with optical grease, the rest of faces were covered with a polytetrafluoroethylene PTFE film tape. A measurement setup produced by Canberra consisted of a PMT R1307, a 2007B scintillation preamplifier, a 2022 spectroscopy amplifier, a 3002D HV power supply, a Multiport II multichannel analyzer and a 2100 NIM Bin/power supply. The shaping time was set to 12 μs , and the PMT voltage was 690 V. A $\text{CsI}(\text{Na})$ crystal of the 25 mm dia. and 25 lengths produced by Amcrys (Ukraine) was taken as a reference sample. The crystal was covered with PTFE film tape and packed into sealed aluminum container with output window.

Scintillation decay times were determined at X-ray excitation (50 kHz excitation repetition rate, FLE 400 filter $\lambda > 400$ nm). The samples were sealed as mentioned in Chapter 2.2. Pulsed X-ray decay measurements were performed using a Hamamatsu N5084 light-excited X-ray tube set at 30 kV as irradiation source. The optical excitation of the tube was performed with a Hamamatsu PLP-10 picosecond light pulser. The scintillation decay was registered by a PMA 165-C PMT from PicoQuant operating in single photon counting regime. According to the data sheet, the transit time is below 180 ps and the rise and fall time are 750 ps providing a time resolution of 180 ps.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Crystal growth

SrI₂:Eu crystals were grown with the different Eu content in the melts – 0.1%, 0.3%, 0.5%, 1%, 2%, 3.5% and 5.5% (Fig. 1). As Eu segregation coefficient in SrI₂ is around unity [8] due to well matched ionic radii of Sr²⁺ and Eu²⁺ and lattice constants of SrI₂ and EuI₂, roughly the same Eu concentrations are assumed in the grown crystals. This was confirmed by the measurements of actual Eu concentrations in crystals (Table 1). The crystal with 5.5% Eu was taken as a reference with the optimal activator concentration according to the prior publications. The crystals were transparent, some of them contained cracks. Some of cracks appeared in the process of extraction from quartz ampoules. Dark inclusions and cracks were observed as a rule just in the tail part of the ingots. The inclusions eventually linked to organic admixtures segregated by the crystallization interface.

Fig. 1. As-grown SrI₂:Eu crystals.

Table 1. Measured concentration of activator in grown crystals.

EuI ₂ concentration (wt. %) in raw materials	EuI ₂ concentration (wt. %) in the grown crystals
0,1%	0.1%

0,3%	0.3%
0,5%	0.5%
1%	1.0%
2%	2.1%
5.5%	5.6%

3.2. Optical parameters

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of SrI₂:Eu samples with the different Eu concentrations (hereafter the values in the legends indicate charging concentrations).

A monotonous increase of Eu concentration in crystals in dependence on activator concentration is confirmed by the $4f^7-4f^65d$ Eu²⁺ absorption band edge redshift due to the increasing intensity of this band (Fig. 2). The UV-excited luminescence spectra of some crystals presented in Fig. 3 contain a typical band corresponding to $4f^65d-4f^7$ transitions in Eu²⁺ ions.

Fig. 3. Luminescence spectra of some $\text{SrI}_2:\text{Eu}$ crystals.

Fig. 4. Decay curves of $\text{SrI}_2:\text{Eu}$ samples under UV excitation (255 nm).

Luminescence decay curves under UV excitation show an overall tendency to shortening of luminescence lifetime with decreasing Eu concentration. Some fluctuations of the radiative lifetimes can be related to not precisely the same dimensions of the samples that affects the

luminescence reabsorption. The curves are fit well by three-exponential decay function (Table 2). The main decay component (τ_2) corresponds to an intrinsic decay time of the 5d-4f transition in Eu^{2+} , which is around 500 ns at room temperature [12]. The slowest decay time (τ_3) exceeding 1000 ns illustrates the luminescence reabsorption process. The fastest decay constant (τ_1) around 40 ns can be ascribed to Eu^{2+} luminescence quenching. In [12] it was suggested that electron from the Eu^{2+} 5d level can be thermally activated into the conduction band and then recombine non-radiatively with a hole. It is clearly seen how the main decay component contribution reinforces with Eu concentration decrease, while reabsorption diminishes.

Table 2. Parameters of luminescence decay under UV excitation obtained by fitting the decay curves by the function $y=y_0+A_1\exp(-t/\tau_1) + A_2\exp(-t/\tau_2)+A_3\exp(-t/\tau_3)$.

Eu concentration (at%) in SrI_2	$\tau_1, \mu\text{s}/A_1$	$\tau_2, \mu\text{s}/A_2$	$\tau_3, \mu\text{s}/A_3$
0.1%	0.041/0.13	0.551/0.83	1.266/0.06
0.3%	0.035/0.13	0.566/0.81	1.395/0.06
0.5%	0.044/0.14	0.472/0.74	1.250/0.12
1%	0.037/0.12	0.638/0.65	1.695/0.23
2%	0.034/0.10	0.643/0.51	1.525/0.39

3.3.Scintillation parameters

Pulse height spectra of the studied series of crystals are presented in Fig. 5. The obtained results demonstrate that with decreasing activator concentration the light output slightly changes within 15% in the 2-5% Eu range and significantly drops at lower Eu concentrations (Fig. 6). All grown crystals in the 0.3-5.5% range of Eu concentrations showed the energy resolution better than 4 % at 662 keV. Even 0.1% Eu sample possesses the energy resolution of 4.4%, which is

better than that in best known NaI:Tl counterparts [13]. This confirms the possibility to reduce significantly the concentration of extremely expensive EuI_2 in commercial $\text{SrI}_2:\text{Eu}$ crystals keeping a very good energy resolution, which is the main parameter for many applications.

Fig. 5. Pulse-shape spectra of $\text{SrI}_2:\text{Eu}$ with the different Eu concentrations at irradiation with 662 keV γ -quanta by ^{137}Cs source.

Fig. 6. Energy resolution (red circles) and light yield (black squares) of $\text{SrI}_2:\text{Eu}$ crystals grown in the present work vs. Eu concentration. The dashed lines show the probable trends. For comparison, the energy resolution of Czochralski grown samples is shown by empty red circles.

As we mentioned in the Introduction, the reason of such high energy resolution of $\text{SrI}_2:\text{Eu}$ at high Eu concentrations is that EuI_2 , besides being an emitting center, plays the role of scavenger of oxygen-containing impurities [10, 11]. Reduced amount of impurities in the feedstock eliminates the need to maintain large concentrations of EuI_2 . Similar scintillation parameters obtained in crystals grown from equally prepared raw materials using the Bridgman-Stockbarger method in this work and Czochralski [9] (see Fig. 6) indicate that the properties of $\text{SrI}_2:\text{Eu}$ do not depend on the crystal growth method.

Fig. 7. Decay curves of some samples under X-ray excitation. The fitted decay constants are 1754 ns at 3.5% Eu, 1022 ns at 0.5% Eu, 746 ns at 0.1% Eu doping.

The faster scintillation decay time at smaller Eu concentrations in $\text{SrI}_2:\text{Eu}$ is an additional reason to reduce the activator concentration (Fig. 7). The monoexponential fit of experimental points confirms the monotonous decrease of main decay constants at decreasing Eu concentration (Fig. 7). These values are in the qualitative agreement with the data on decay times in dependence on activator Eu concentration in $\text{SrI}_2:\text{Eu}$ reported in [9, 12], and confirm the reduction of the self-absorption phenomena in weakly doped crystals. Note the significant pile-up observed in the 0.1 Eu% sample due to an increase of the carrier diffusion distance to activator centers at X-ray excitation. The monoexponential fit of experimental points gives the similar decay constants of 1.02 μs and 0.98 μs for 0.5% Eu samples fabricated from the Bridgman-Stockbarger and Czochralski-grown crystals, respectively (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. X-ray excited luminescence decay in 0.5% Eu activated samples fabricated from Bridgman-Stockbarger- and Czochralski- grown crystals.

The X-ray luminescence spectra contain the main peak corresponding to the $5d-4f$ radiative transitions in Eu^{2+} (Fig. 9). The peak redshifts by around 10 nm due to reabsorption with the increase of Eu concentration (see the inset in Fig. 9). Meanwhile, the Eu^{2+} emission band of 5.5% Eu sample is split into two peaks, evidently, certifying an inhomogeneity of Eu^{2+} distribution over the crystals, namely the presence of regions with higher and lower Eu concentrations. The 0.1% Eu sample spectrum reveals both Eu^{2+} and an intense green luminescence band observed also in pure SrI_2 and attributed to self-trapped excitons (STEs) [12]. The probability of STE formation increases with decreasing Eu concentration, thus affecting the Eu^{2+} luminescence efficiency [12].

Fig. 9. X-ray luminescence spectra of SrI_2 crystals with different Eu content. Inset: the enlarged view of Eu^{2+} luminescence peaks.

Conclusions

The obtained results indicate the possibility of revising the required amount of activator in $\text{SrI}_2:\text{Eu}$ crystals and significantly reduce the cost of crystalline scintillation detectors. The Eu concentration can be decreased down to 0.1-0.5% without a major degradation of energy resolution, which is the main parameter determining the efficiency of detector in scintillation spectrometry. The energy resolution at 663 keV remains below 4% in the concentration range down to 0.3% of Eu, meanwhile the light yield decreases just within 15% decreasing the Eu concentration from 5.5 to 2%. Another advantage of light-doped $\text{SrI}_2:\text{Eu}$ is a faster scintillation decay time. The obtained results also showed that the scintillation parameters of light-doped $\text{SrI}_2:\text{Eu}$ do not depend on the method of its preparation (Czochralski or Bridgman-Stockbarger technology).

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